

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 4, Issue 3 (2026)

Vasectomy and Its Impact on Testicular and Epididymal Morphology in Male Rabbits

Ikram Ullah¹, Ali Imran², Ehsan Ullah Zimri³, Saffa Qasim⁴, Sundas Arif⁵, Abdur Rahman⁶, Ghulam Shabir Barham⁷, Shakeel Ahmed Tunio⁸, Jahanzaib Khaliq^{9*}, Saqib Saleem Abdullah¹⁰

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Unilateral and Bilateral, Kashmir Vasectomy, Rabbit, Testicles, Epididymis, Ultrasonography

Ikram Ullah

Department of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry, Faculty of Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Sciences, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam

Email: drikramullahikram@gmail.com

Ali Imran

UMW, PCSIR Labs, Complex, Lahore

Ehsan Ullah Zimri

Institute of Physiology and Pharmacology, University of Faisalabad

Saffa Qasim

Department of Biosciences, Comsats University Islamabad

Sundas Arif

Department of Veterinary Clinical Sciences, University of Ponch, Rawalakot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

Abdur Rahman

Department of Veterinary and Medicine, Faculty of Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Sciences, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam

Ghulam Shabir Barham

Department of Animal Products Technology, Faculty of Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Sciences, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam

Email: gsbarham@sau.edu.pk

Shakeel Ahmed Tunio

Department of Livestock and Management, Faculty of Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Sciences, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam

Email: satunio@sau.edu.pk

Jahanzaib Khaliq*

Department of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry, Faculty of Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Sciences, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam

Email: jahanzaibvet@gmail.com

Saqib Saleem Abdullah

Department of Veterinary Basic Sciences, University of Ponch, Rawalakot, Azad Jammu and

Kashmir

Background: Vasectomy is a common surgical method used for male sterilization by cutting or blocking the vas deferens. Studying its effects in rabbits helps understand how this procedure influences on structure of testicle and epididymis. This research provides useful information about reproductive track morphology and potential impacts on male fertility.

Objectives: To evaluate how vasectomy affects the structure of testicle and epididymis in male rabbits to understand its impact on reproductive morphology.

Methodology: Six pairs (n=12) mature adult male rabbits weighing 1.42±0.09 kg were recruited for the experiment. Animals were divided into three experimental groups, and each group consisted of four rabbits. One control group (sham operated), second unilateral vasectomy group and third bilateral vasectomy group. Experimental vasectomy was done carefully unilateral in second group and bilateral in third group. Morphological changes in testis and epididymis such as length, width, circumference were measured and recorded by ultrasound machine with 2.5 -12 MHz frequency linear probe of 2D imaging at the 15 days of vasectomy operation with an interval of each 15 day for 12 weeks. Data was analyzed using software STATIX-10 by ONE-WAY ANOVA with Turkeys test to compare between the groups and results expressed as mean + SD.

Results: The present study presents that there is no biometric change in testicles and epididymis length, width and circumstances of unilateral vasectomized and bilateral vasectomized group as compared to control group. Statistically, there were significantly no keywords in unilateral vasectomy and bilateral vasectomy, testicles and epididymis size and shape.

Conclusion: Overall, it is concluded that there is no significant alteration in morphology of testicles and epididymis in unilateral vasectomy and bilateral vasectomy.

INTRODUCTION

Population explosion One of the most significant issues facing the entire globe nowadays Vasectomy is a widely used and recognized method of male contraception to control the population boom. According to Ali et al. (2022) and Amory et al. (2020), 60–100 million men worldwide utilize vasectomy as a method of pregnancy control. Vasectomy has great potential to be recommended in investigating the structure and performance of epididymis. The mechanism is associated clearly with understanding the previous data on the basic controlling of the structure process. After leaving the testis, the spermatozoa pass along the epididymis to gain full fertilizing potential (James et al., 2020; Roberts et al., 1995).

Vasectomy is now widely accepted as a safe and dependable method of contraception for couples (Schwingl and Guess, 2000; Cox et al., 2002). Vasectomy is used by more than 40 million couples worldwide to terminate pregnancy. This process is quick and trusty with low rates long-term complication, i.e., in the rank 0.08–0.10%. Vasectomy is a surgical procedure to cut and tied vasa deferentia for male neutering to stop fertilization of a female through sexual intercourse. Vasectomy is a method used successfully worldwide for male contraception and in 2015 in the United States approximately 527,476 vasectomies were utilized. An evolution of trend for use of vasectomy revealed that 82% of vasectomies were performed during 2014 and 2015 in USA (Ostrowski et al., 2018). In the United States compared to female contraception, male neutering (vasectomy) is the most efficacious, with lesser ratio of complications low cost effective and only long-acting form of contraception. Along these advantages, in the United States of America, vasectomy is performed at low than half the ratio of female neutering. In addition, it is utilized at less numbers among the populations of Latino and Black, as compared to female neutering (Shihi et al., 2011).

The unusual growth of population is recognized as an alarming situation to the international community. It is high obstructions for socioeconomic growth. Vasectomy is one of the techniques to control the population by offering reliable procedure of contraception and which has been approved by the World Health Organization (Hosseini and Abdi, 2012) in different countries and religions there are religious and ethical challenges beside different issues for family planning, contraception, abortion, female sterilization and male vasectomy. Presently, all over the world to prevent pregnancy about more than 40 million twosomes rely on it (Vrijhof et al., 2004).

The vas deference is a structure of tube shape comprises of a mucosal inner layer and three muscular layers that carry sperm to the ejaculatory duct from the cauda epididymis. In this surgical procedure luminal continuity of the vas deferens is interrupted and thus interferes with transportation of spermatozoa from the testis and epididymis into the urethra. Injury to the vas deference during vasectomy may affect negatively on male fertility resulting from enlarged diameter of seminiferous tubular, sperm maturing process and obstruction of spermatogenesis (Singh and Charvarty, 2000; Duru et al., 2013). The vas deferens unilateral ligation results in a bilateral flaw in spermatogenesis and in the epididymal sperm maturation procedure (Ikeda and Nikolaos, 2000). In their study observed post vasectomy motility, declines in sperm count and other morphological aberrations seen in sperm morphology (Kim et al., 2001; Ullah et al., 2025).

The side effects such as, painful nodules, sperm granuloma and the stasis of epididymis (Huang et al., 2010). Vasectomy experiments on testis of rat, guinea pig, and monkey revealed that histoarchitectural changes in testis occurs after vasectomy. Vasectomy in rat, guinea pig, rabbit, dog and monkey has shown regression of seminiferous tubules. Singh and Charvarty (2000) observed the presence of macrophages in the lumen of the rete testis and seminiferous tubes of the vasectomized rat that reflected the elimination of degenerated spermatozoa. In the seminiferous tubules of Vasectomized mice showed degenerative changes; these changes include tubules vacuolations, basement membrane thickening and sloughing of immature germ cells in the tubules. Lumens of several seminiferous tubules had sloughed spermatogenic cells and enormous quantities of spermatids. Highly congested blood vessels were present in the interstitial tissue of few sections and big necrotic parts covering certain of the tubules together with the eosinophilic material (edema) of intertubular and with the scant mononuclear cell's infiltration. Germ cells were seen in disarray of few tubules

were not properly developed. Various tubules were near entirely damaged (with spermatogenic cells vacuoles) leaving outsized areas of interstitial space edema and few testes showed numerous interstitial fibrosis with the tubules vacuolations and thickening of the basement membrane (Salman et al., 2012). Alteration in sperm morphology and motility and declination in sperm count and testosterone level was the result of histoarchitectural damage in the vasectomized animals (Duru et al., 2013).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals and Study Site

Twelve apparently clinically and healthy, adult rabbits about 408±14.7 days of age, weighing 1.42±0.09 kg body weight were purchased from open market of Hyderabad and kept at animal house of Faculty of Animal Husbandry, SAU, Tandojam.

Experimental design

After an adaptation period of two weeks all rabbits were grouped as control (group-1), unilateral vasectomy (group-2) and bilateral vasectomy (group-3). Then the rabbits were tagged according to their weight and divided into three groups Group-1 (Control) n=4, [blue color tag=1, 2, 3, 4], Group-2 (Unilateral Vasectomy) n=4 [green color tag=5, 6, 7, 8]. Group-3 (Bilateral Vasectomy) n=4 [white color tag= 9, 10, 11, 12]. Rabbits of all groups were kept under observation in different cages. Vasectomy operations were performed in hygienic environment, anesthesia to each rabbit of unilateral vasectomized group-2 and bilateral vasectomized group-3 were induced by intramuscular injection of ketamine and xylazine at a dose 35 mg/kg and 5 mg/kg respectively. In the vasectomy a scrotal incision was made to expose the vas deferens, about 2 to 3 cm length of it were cut out with the two ends ligated. After operations, each rabbit was treated with 80,000-unit penicillin with intramuscular injection for three days and kept the wounds dry with pyodine to avoid infection. The rabbits were raised as routine in the animal house center. Data collection started on the 15th day after operation with an interval of 15 days for 12 weeks. Pre – vasectomy and post –vasectomy rabbits of group G1, G2 and G3 were restrained manually, positioned on dorsal recumbency Morphological changes in testis and epididymis such as length, width, circumstance was measured and recorded by ultrasound machine with 2.5 -12 MHz frequency linear probe of 2D imaging.

(a)

(b)

Figure :1a, b, c, and d, Male Reproductive System of Rabbits

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data obtained were analyzed using software STATIX-10 by ONE-WAY ANOVA with Turkeys test to compare between the groups and results expressed as mean + SD.

RESULTS

Biometry of Testicles

Ultrasonographic biometry of length, width and circumference of testicles is given in (Table 1 Figure 2a). The mean length of testicles by ultrasonography was 40.75+5.12 mm in group-1, 43.00+5.03 mm in group-2 and 41.75+4.92 mm in group-3 whereas, mean width of testicle was 19.25 +5.25 mm in group-1, 21.00+ 2.58 mm in group-2 and 23.25+4.64 mm in group-3. Mean circumference of testicles through ultrasonography was 125.50 + 5.19 in group-1, 131.00 + 2.58 mm in group-2 and 130.75+9.42 mm in group-3. Statistically, there was no significant difference in length, width and circumference of testicles of group-1, group-2 and group-3 rabbits, but we can say that group-3 testicles are atrophied due to degenerative structural changes, likely associated with edema, fibrosis, and loss of functional parenchyma rather than true hypertrophy (Figure 2b).

Table: 1 Ultrasonographic biometry of testicles of group-1, group-2 and group-3

Variable	N	Mean			SD		
		Length	Width	Circumference	Length	Width	Circumference
Group1	4	40.75 ^b	19.25 ^c	125.50 ^a	±5.1235	±5.2520	±5.1962
Group2	4	43.00 ^b	21.00 ^c	131.00 ^a	±5.0332	±2.5820	±2.5820
Group3	4	41.75 ^b	23.25 ^c	130.75 ^a	±4.9244	±4.6458	±9.4296

P<0.05

LSD 12.644

Figure :2a Ultrasonographic biometry of testicles of group-1, group-2 and group-3

Figure :2b Ultrasonographic biometry of testicles of group-1, group-2 and group-3

Biometry of Epididymis

Table 2 and Figure 3 show the ultrasonographic biometry of length, width and circumference of epididymis. The mean length of epididymis by ultrasonography was 28.500±4.7958 mm in group-1, 25.750±2.5000 mm in group-2 and 25.250±4.9244 mm in group-3. Whereas mean width of epididymis was 15.250±2.5000 mm in group-1, 14.750±2.5000 mm in group-2 and 18.000±3.5590 mm in group-3. Mean circumference of epididymis through ultrasonography was 57.750±6.3443 in group-1, 64.500±2.8868 mm in group-2 and 62.250±4.9244 mm in group-3. Statistically, there was no significant difference in length, width and circumference of epididymis of group-1, group-2 and group-3 rabbits.

Table: 2: Ultrasonographic biometry of epididymis of group-1, group-2 and group-3

Variable	N	Mean			SD		
		Length	Width	Circumference	Length	Width	Circumference
Group1	4	28.500 ^b	15.250 ^d	57.750 ^a	±4.7958	±2.5000	±6.3443
Group2	4	25.750 ^{bc}	14.750 ^d	64.500 ^a	±2.5000	±2.5000	±2.8868
Group3	4	25.250 ^{bc}	18.000 ^{cd}	62.250 ^a	±4.9244	±3.5590	±4.9244

P≤0.05

LSD 9.7604

Figure: 3 Ultrasonographic biometry of epididymis of group-1, group-2 and group-3

DISCUSSION

Present study was conducted to investigate the effects of unilateral and bilateral vasectomy on the gross morphological changes in testicle and epididymis, semen physico-chemical properties, and male gonadal hormone concentration. Ultrasonographic measurements of testicles morphology, revealed that there was no significant change in length, width and circumference. There was slight increase in length, width and circumference of epididymis. No significant changes were recorded in length, width and circumference of testicles between control group1 and group 2 unilaterally vasectomized, bilateral vasectomized group 3 rabbits. Both width and circumference of epididymis of rabbits in group 3 were found increased as compared to control group. Sepaan and Krishnaswamy (2014) have reported gross alteration in testicles and epididymis in long term vasectomized bonnet monkey (*Macaca radiata*). Results of present studies are in accordance with those of Sepaan and Krishnaswamy (2014), they attributed these changes to the accumulation of sperm and the tight fibrous capsule which could have produced the observed dimensional change in testis and epididymis.

These results agree with the findings of Lohiya et al. (1983) who reported that long-term vasectomy in rabbits did not produce major structural changes in the seminiferous tubules, and the epididymal epithelium largely retained normal characteristics. Their study suggested that despite vasectomy, overall structural integrity remains preserved, which supports the absence of significant morphological differences observed in the present study. Similarly, Peng et al. (2008) found in a rabbit model that vasectomy performed via the inguinal canal did not lead to significant histological damage to spermatogenesis when compared to contralateral sham-operated sides, although the juxta-epididymal vas deferens exhibited notable fluid

distension. This aligns with the lack of significant gross morphological differences observed in the present study.

Similarly, Kong et al. (2004) found that although some early alterations in spermatogenesis may occur after vasectomy, testicular structure and epididymal size often show no statistically significant long-term differences compared to controls. Their morphometric analysis further indicated that epididymal enlargement observed in some cases was not significant, which aligns with the minor, non-significant variations recorded in this study. Moreover, studies by Flickinger et al. (1990) emphasized that vasectomy mainly induces functional and microscopic changes, such as increased resorptive activity, rather than gross anatomical changes in the epididymis. Similarly, Ma et al. (2016) reported that while seminiferous tubule structure and sperm granuloma formation varied among mature rats after vasectomy, morphometric assessments did not show consistent enlargement of the epididymis or major anatomical distortions as a universal outcome.

CONCLUSION

Overall results showed some changes in length, width and circumference of testicle and epididymis of vasectomized rabbits as compared to control group. However, there was no significant difference between groups.

Authors' Contribution

IU is researcher and author of manuscript. JK and AI supervised the study. EUZ, SQ, SA guided to conduct research in laboratory. GSB and SAT helped in formal analysis. AR, SSA contributed to manuscript writing, reviews, and editing.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The original data of study is available and there was not any special source of funding.

REFERENCES

- Ali Thoufekar A Imeer, A. A. H. K. (2022). Morphological, Histological, and Ultrastructural Changes in Epididymis after a Vasectomy. *Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences*, 49(4).
- Amory, J. K. (2020). Development of novel male contraceptives. *Clinical and translational science*, 13(2), 228-237. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cts.12708>
- Cox, B., Sneyd, M. J., Paul, C., Delahunt, B., & Skegg, D. C. (2002). Vasectomy and risk of prostate cancer. *Jama*, 287(23), 3110-3115. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.287.23.3110>
- Duru, F. I. O., Ajayi, S., & Azu, O. O. (2013). The effect of unilateral vasectomy on testosterone and testicular parameters in the adult male African giant rat (*Cricetomys gambianus*). *African Health Sciences*, 13(2), 483-489. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v13i2.40>
- Flickinger, C. J., Herr, J. C., Caloras, D., Sisak, J. R., & Howards, S. S. (1990). Inflammatory changes in the epididymis after vasectomy in the Lewis rat. *Biology of reproduction*, 43(1), 34-45. <https://doi.org/10.1095/biolreprod43.1.34>
- Hosseini, H., & Abdi, F. (2012). Experiences of vasectomy: a phenomenological study. *North American Journal of Medical Sciences*, 4(12), 619.
- Huang, X. B., Suo, J. P., Chen, C. Y., Du, Q. L., Shen, J. Y., & Zhou, J. L. (2010). Initial studies on a novel filtering-type intra-vas device in male dogs. *Contraception*, 81(4), 350-354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2009.10.012>

- Ikedo, T., & Sofikitis, N. (2000). Bilateral testicular consequences in the unilateral vasectomy of immature rats. *Yonago Acta Medica*, 43(1), 1-9.
- James, E. R., Carrell, D. T., Aston, K. I., Jenkins, T. G., Yeste, M., & Salas-Huetos, A. (2020). The role of the epididymis and the contribution of epididymosomes to mammalian reproduction. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 21(15), 5377. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21155377>
- Kim, J. M., Ghosh, S. R., Weil, A. C., & Zirkin, B. R. (2001). Caspase-3 and caspase-activated deoxyribonuclease are associated with testicular germ cell apoptosis resulting from reduced intratesticular testosterone. *Endocrinology*, 142(9), 3809-3816. <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.142.9.3809>
- Kong, L. S., Huang, A. P., Deng, X. Z., & Yang, Z. W. (2004). Quantitative (stereological) study of the effects of vasectomy on spermatogenesis in rabbits. *Journal of anatomy*, 205(2), 147-156. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0021-8782.2004.00322.x>
- Lohiya, N. K., Mathur, N., Tiwari, S. N., & Shipstone, A. C. (1983). Ultrastructural changes in rabbit testis and epididymis following vasectomy: a long term study. *Acta europaea fertilitatis*, 14(2), 141-146.
- Ma, L., Guo, Y., Yuan, Y., Li, Y. G., Deng, X. Z., & Yang, Z. W. (2016). Morphometric study of the testis and reproductive tract (including sperm granuloma) after vasectomy in mature rats. *Asian Journal of Andrology*, 18(1), 66-73. 10.4103/1008-682X.150038
- de Oliveira, F. B., Pereira, V. X., Oliveira, F. R., de Abreu, L. C., Daboin, B. E. G., Norberto, A. R., ... & Glina, S. (2018). Effect of ductus deferens lavage on the time to achieve azoospermia in patients undergoing vasectomy. *Clinics*, 73, e504. <https://doi.org/10.6061/clinics/2018/e504>
- Ostrowski, K. A., Holt, S. K., Haynes, B., Davies, B. J., Fuchs, E. F., & Walsh, T. J. (2018). Evaluation of vasectomy trends in the United States. *Urology*, 118, 76-79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.urology.2018.03.016>
- Peng, B., Wang, Y. P., Shang, Y., Guo, Y., & Yang, Z. W. (2008). Effect of vasectomy via inguinal canal on spermatogenesis in rabbits. *Asian journal of andrology*, 10(3), 486-493. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-7262.2008.00394.x>
- Roberts, K. P. (1995). WHAT ARE THE COMPONENTS OF THE MALE REPRODUCTIVE-SYSTEM. *Journal of Andrology*, 1-4.
- Salman, M. O., Al-Wasiti, E. A., Thamir, K. A., Al-Ani, I. M., & Al-Salihi, A. R. (2012). The effects of vasectomy on testicular tissue of mice: histological changes and DNA fragmentation study. *IJUM Medical Journal Malaysia*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.31436/imjm.v11i2.522>
- Schwingl, P. J., & Guess, H. A. (2000). Safety and effectiveness of vasectomy. *Fertility and sterility*, 73(5), 923-936. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0015-0282\(00\)00482-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0015-0282(00)00482-9)
- Seppan, P., & Krishnaswamy, K. (2014). Long-term study of vasectomy in *Macaca radiata*—histological and ultrasonographic analysis of testis and duct system. *Systems Biology in Reproductive Medicine*, 60(3), 151-160. <https://doi.org/10.3109/19396368.2014.896957>
- Shih, G., Turok, D. K., & Parker, W. J. (2011). Vasectomy: the other (better) form of sterilization. *Contraception*, 83(4), 310-315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2010.08.019>
- Singh, S. K., & Chakravarty, S. (2000). Histologic changes in the mouse testis after bilateral vasectomy. *Asian journal of andrology*, 2(2), 115-120.
- Ullah, I., Kachiwal, A. B., Soomro, S. A., Haseeb, A., Khaliq, J., Ismail, M., ... & Ullah10, M. INVESTIGATION OF SURGICAL VASECTOMY EFFECTS ON SEMINAL AND HORMONAL PROFILES IN MALE RABBITS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18092481>
- Vrijhof, E. J., de Bruïne, A., à Nijeholt, A. A. L., & Koole, L. H. (2004). A polymeric mini-stent designed to facilitate the vasectomy reversal operation. A rabbit model study. *Biomaterials*, 25(4), 729-734. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612\(03\)00569-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612(03)00569-6)